

Simulation-based techno-economic optimization of continuous ibuprofen manufacturing under uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

A robust techno-economic assessment is essential to evaluate and facilitate the adoption of continuous manufacturing technologies, as well as to guide process development. We present a novel framework for uncertainty-aware techno-economic assessment. This framework combines conceptual process design and simulation, global sensitivity analysis, stochastic optimization, and economic evaluation under uncertainty in a unified workflow. We apply the framework to the continuous manufacturing of ibuprofen, which is predominantly manufactured through established batch processes, and benchmark its performance against a conventional deterministic optimization approach. While the deterministic optimization converges more rapidly to a lower levelized cost of production (LCOP) for the base-case price, the stochastic approach provides a more conservative, robust solution, reflecting real-world process variability. The resulting optimized design remains economically competitive, with an LCOP below current market prices, while ensuring greater reliability under uncertainty. By capturing variability in economic parameters, our approach enhances decision-making and facilitates exploration of conceptual design performance under uncertainty. This comparison highlights the importance of integrating uncertainty quantification into technology shifts and strategic process development.

1. Introduction

The pharmaceutical industry faces increasing pressure to enhance productivity, improve process efficiency, reduce costs, and minimize environmental impacts. Traditionally, the pharmaceutical industry has relied on batch manufacturing for large-scale active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) production, which often involves high operational costs, extended production times, and significant raw material and energy consumption. As a result, there has been a growing shift toward continuous manufacturing, which offers improved scalability, enhanced process control, reduced solvent usage, and energy and cost savings (Anderson, 2012; Hugh and Rooney, 2010). To support the adoption of these new technologies and the continued development of these processes to fully benefit from the advantages, systematic evaluation of process alternatives and the identification of optimal configurations are crucial. Techno-economic assessment (TEA) plays a vital role in this context, enabling the evaluation of profitability, identification of cost drivers, and mitigation of financial risks associated with transitioning to continuous pharmaceutical processes.

While experimental verification and process validation at pilot plant

scale remain important for demonstrating the feasibility and viability of the processes, they are labor-intensive, costly, and time-consuming. Process simulators address these challenges by replacing high-cost laboratory experiments and pilot plant studies with simulation models that explore alternative designs efficiently and predict process behavior for new technologies before making substantial investments. By integrating accurate thermodynamic models, kinetic data, and process constraints, simulations provide valuable insights into the feasibility and performance of chemical processes across different scales. Coupling simulations with optimization techniques unlocks their full potential, allowing systematic exploration of the design space, identification of optimal conditions, and improvements in metrics like yield, productivity, energy efficiency, and cost-effectiveness. While simulation-based optimization offers significant advantages, computational time can be substantial, especially for complex simulation models, due to the need to run numerous simulation tasks; therefore, using advanced sampling and surrogate modeling becomes essential for efficient convergence to near-optimal solutions (Bhosekar and Ierapetritou, 2018).

Surrogate-based optimization techniques are effective for navigating these complexities, yet conventional deterministic optimization

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approaches often overlook variability in factors such as raw material costs, reaction kinetics, operating conditions, and market demands that can significantly impact the economic and technical feasibility of processes. Incorporating uncertainty quantification is thus critical, particularly in TEA for pharmaceutical manufacturing, especially during the transition to new technologies like continuous manufacturing, to develop robust solutions that perform reliably in real-world scenarios. Cheali et al. (2015) highlighted that neglecting uncertainties in capital cost estimation can result in suboptimal designs, while Barahmand and Eikeland (2022) emphasized the need for uncertainty-aware TEA frameworks to enhance decision-making reliability. Stochastic simulation-based optimization has emerged as a powerful method to address this, with Monte Carlo techniques providing probabilistic assessments of performance metrics (Kalos and Whitlock, 2008). Hoffmann et al. (2004) introduced response surface-based methods for early-stage technology assessment under uncertainty, offering an efficient surrogate modeling approach that paved the way for advanced stochastic optimization techniques. Building on these, the work of Al et al. (2020) introduces MOSKopt, a MATLAB®-based stochastic simulation-based optimization solver that integrates global sensitivity analysis, Monte Carlo simulations, and Kriging-based optimization to systematically explore process alternatives while ensuring robustness in performance. Global sensitivity analysis identifies the most influential process parameters, while Monte Carlo simulations provide a probabilistic assessment of process variability. Stochastic Kriging (SK), introduced by Ankenman et al. (2010), improves computational efficiency by modeling the process responses while accounting for uncertainty.

This study advances these foundations by presenting a novel framework for robust TEA of continuous pharmaceutical manufacturing. The framework integrates AVEVA™ for process simulation with a Python-based MOSKopt implementation, enabling optimization under uncertainty at an industrial scale. This approach supports data-driven decision-making with comprehensive insights into the critical trade-offs between profitability, performance, and risk by evaluating process robustness against variability. We apply this framework to the continuous manufacturing of ibuprofen, a widely used nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) traditionally produced via batch processes, enhancing the preliminary optimization of the ibuprofen hydrogenation step focused on reaction yields and kinetic parameter uncertainties (Asrav et al., 2024).

Prior studies have laid important groundwork for assessing the economic viability and energy efficiency of transitioning ibuprofen production from batch to continuous modes, using diverse modeling approaches and scales. For instance, Jolliffe and Gerogiorgis (2015) developed a steady-state model for 50 kg/year continuous production, demonstrating potential for enhanced energy efficiency, cost reductions, and lower environmental impacts. Hasan et al. (2019) conducted a TEA of a 44 metric ton per year ibuprofen plant using Aspen®, providing insights into investment opportunities. Mustafa et al. (2022) developed a process model and conducted a TEA using SuperPro Designer®, focusing on a green synthesis route for a scale of 5000 metric tonnes per year. Their work incorporated Raoult's law with Wilson coefficients for thermodynamic modeling. Tripodi et al. (2020) emphasized the role of thermodynamic models in accurate process representation using ibuprofen continuous manufacturing as an example. More recently, Ince et al. (2025) conducted a comprehensive TEA and life-cycle assessment comparing batch and flow syntheses across multiple APIs, including ibuprofen, highlighting the sustainability gains of continuous processes.

While prior studies establish valuable benchmarks through deterministic point estimates, they evaluate a single design case without searching the decision space for an economic optimum. Our work advances these contributions by integrating advanced stochastic optimization with explicit uncertainty quantification into the TEA, extending the scope to enable variability-aware decision-making for large-scale continuous manufacturing. This approach introduces a comprehensive framework that builds on established insights, enhances process

robustness, and supports confident investments. This framework develops a rigorous process model in AVEVA™, incorporating detailed thermodynamic models, comprehensive kinetic data for each reaction step, and mass/energy balances to accurately simulate the continuous ibuprofen synthesis pathway, ensuring high-fidelity predictions under varying operational conditions. It then conducts a global sensitivity analysis followed by stochastic optimization under uncertainty, which is benchmarked against a deterministic approach to demonstrate the value of incorporating variability. Specifically, we seek to identify a process design that minimizes the leveled cost of production (LCOP) of ibuprofen while satisfying constraints on overall process yield and reactor residence times.

Section 2 introduces the steps included in the proposed framework, and Section 3 demonstrates the application of every step of the framework to ibuprofen continuous manufacturing. Section 4 presents the discussion of the results, and finally, Section 5 summarizes the main outcomes and discusses the potential future use of the framework.

2. Framework for robust techno-economic assessment

A rigorous process model developed using AVEVA™ process simulation software forms the foundation of this framework, illustrated in Fig. 1. This model, based on mass and energy balances, simulates the process behavior under various operating conditions using accurate thermodynamic models and kinetic data for reliable simulation results. The AVEVA™ Economics tool considers embedded costing equations, which allow for the evaluation of the process's economic performance throughout the simulation and optimization process.

The framework includes global sensitivity analysis to identify the uncertain parameters and variables that have the greatest impact on economic performance. This step helps prioritize the uncertain parameters for detailed uncertainty quantification. Uncertainties in cost parameters are quantified by assigning appropriate probability distributions. The optimization problem is formulated, including the decision variables, objective function, and constraints.

The simulation-based optimization is performed using a Python implementation of the MOSKopt framework developed by Al et al. (2020), and it is connected to the AVEVA™ process simulation software via the AVEVA Python interface. Fig. 1 demonstrates the internal structure of the MOSKopt framework. This framework employs a Bayesian optimization strategy based on surrogate modeling to efficiently explore the design space with fewer simulations. Initially, a set of design points is generated using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). A Stochastic Kriging (SK) model is then trained with simulations obtained using these initial samples. In practice, the Stochastic Kriging model is implemented using Gaussian Process regression to predict both the mean response and the variance, based on Monte Carlo simulation outputs. A separate noise model is trained to capture the standard deviation of the outputs, enabling the surrogate to handle both intrinsic and extrinsic uncertainty. After the initial SK model is constructed, adaptive sampling follows to find the optimum values. The Multiple Constrained Feasibility Enhanced Expected Improvement (mcFEI) infill criterion is used for adaptive sampling. This criterion provides a measure of the expected improvement at a new design point compared to the current best point, and it effectively considers the probability of feasibility for each stochastic constraint while simultaneously seeking improvements in the objective function (Al et al., 2020). The mcFEI criterion is optimized using particle swarm optimization to efficiently identify new sampling points. The surrogate model is updated with these points at each iteration to improve the accuracy of the model. This continues until the termination criterion is reached.

To account for uncertainties in the optimization process, Monte Carlo simulations are integrated within the Python framework. For each design point considered during the optimization, multiple Monte Carlo simulations are run, sampling from the distributions assigned to the uncertain parameters. A probabilistic constraint handling strategy

Fig. 1. Framework for simulation-based techno-economic optimization

(mean plus one standard deviation) is employed to ensure robust performance in the face of uncertainty. Specifically, the mean plus one standard deviation of the constraint observations from the Monte Carlo simulations is kept below the constraint limit. This approach incorporates both the average performance and the associated risk into the decision-making process, leading to more robust solutions that are less sensitive to variations in the uncertain parameters (Wang and Ierapetritou, 2018). Given that the mean value of Monte Carlo simulations converges to the true value, we evaluate the objective function and constraints based on this mean value. From all observations, we then select the best feasible design point according to the objective function. Finally, the framework concludes with a techno-economic evaluation based on the optimized design. The TEA focuses on interpreting the resulting process configuration and the key economic metric under uncertainty. Since uncertainty is already integrated into the optimization process via Monte Carlo simulations, the final design reflects not only cost-efficiency but also robustness to uncertainty in critical economic and process parameters. This enables an informed assessment of performance across a range of possible operating conditions, while also providing confidence in the expected performance outcomes.

3. Application to Ibuprofen synthesis

3.1. Process design and simulation

Ibuprofen is synthesized through a two-step catalytic process, involving the hydrogenation of 4-isobutyl acetophenone (IBAP) to 1-(4-isobutylphenyl)-ethanol (IBPE), followed by the carbonylation of IBPE to ibuprofen (Elango et al., 1990). While IBAP is typically synthesized from isobutylbenzene via Friedel–Crafts acylation, this upstream step is excluded from the system boundary due to the lack of publicly available kinetic data. Instead, we assume IBAP is externally purchased as a feedstock. We model and simulate the continuous ibuprofen manufacturing process in the AVEVA™ process simulator, performing rigorous mass and energy balances of the different unit process operations. Our modeling approach utilizes the NRTL (Non-Random Two-Liquid) model for liquid-liquid equilibrium unit operations and the SRK (Soave-Redlich-Kwong) equation of state for vapor-liquid equilibrium-based separation processes. To address compounds with missing data, we use the UNIFAC (Universal Quasi-Chemical Functional Group Activity Coefficients) group contribution method to estimate their properties. The interaction parameters are provided in Section A of the [Supplementary Material](#). These models are critical for accurately predicting phase behavior, component distribution, and energy requirements across various unit operations, particularly in the separation

and purification steps.

3.1.1. Upstream processes

We model the hydrogenation of 4-isobutyl acetophenone (IBAP) with hydrogen over a heterogeneous Pd/SiO₂ catalyst using a plug-flow reactor (PFR) under isothermal conditions. We adopt the reaction steps from Thakar et al. (2007) and use decane as the solvent.

We model the carbonylation of 1-(4-isobutylphenyl) ethanol (IBPE) using a homogeneous PdI₂(PPh₃)₂/TsOH/LiCl catalyst in a plug-flow reactor (PFR) under isothermal conditions. We adopt the reaction steps from Seayad et al. (2003) and use methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) as the solvent.

The reaction kinetics reported in Thakar et al. (2007) and Seayad et al. (2003) are further refined by Montes et al. (2018), who performed parameter identifiability analysis and re-estimation using dynamic plantwide simulation data. We adopt the updated parameters provided by Montes et al. for our model implementation in this work. These parameters are provided in Section B of the [Supplementary Material](#).

3.1.2. Downstream processes

Downstream separation and purification steps ensure high product purity and efficient solvent recovery. The first separation stage, following the hydrogenation reaction, uses a distillation column and a flash drum to recover and recycle the solvent decane while also removing water. The carbonylation reaction results in the formation of two immiscible phases: aqueous and organic, which must be separated to enable catalyst recovery. This phase separation is initiated using a decanter, with ethyl acetate added to improve phase separation (Wang and Ierapetritou, 2018). A subsequent distillation column recovers and recycles the solvent, methyl ethyl ketone. An additional vacuum distillation step follows to remove residual organic impurities (Zey et al., 1992). Final purification is achieved through crystallization. We model the continuous vacuum crystallizer as a continuous stirred tank

reactor (CSTR) in AVEVA™, using ethanol as the solvent. The solubility-temperature relationship employed in CSTR is described by the modified Apelblat equation as follows (Wang et al., 2010):

$$\ln(x_{\text{ibuprofen}}) = 0.289367 - 2605.96/T + 1.19778 \ln(T) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2 illustrates the process flowsheet including the upstream and downstream processes.

3.2. Global sensitivity analysis

To identify the parameters that most significantly impact the overall economic performance of the ibuprofen manufacturing process, we perform a global sensitivity analysis on LCOP. This analysis focuses on key economic variables: Lang Factor, equipment, raw material, solvent, and catalyst prices, utility costs, annual labor cost, maintenance cost, and project lifetime. This ensures direct relevance to our primary economic objective, and the analysis helps prioritize which uncertainties require more detailed quantification. The analysis applies a regression-based method, Standardized Regression Coefficients (SRC) calculated from 1000 LHS samples (Saltelli et al., 2008). This method is well-suited for the highly linear nature of the LCOP model for fixed process design and operating variables. For this analysis, the uncertain parameters listed in Table S5 in Section D of the Supplementary Material are assumed to follow uniform distributions using the base prices in Table S6. Fig. 3 presents the SRC values, highlighting the 15 parameters with the strongest influence. An additional figure, Figure S1, showing a detailed breakdown of parameter impact on capital expenditures, operating expenditures, and LCOP through one-at-a-time (OAT) analysis, is provided in Section D of the Supplementary Material.

For the subsequent uncertainty analysis, we consider parameters with the highest sensitivity impact, and the IBAP price proved to be the most critical uncertainty compared to other variables, as shown in Fig. 3. This high sensitivity to IBAP price is logical, as the process assumes external procurement of this feedstock, making its market fluctuations a direct and significant cost driver for the LCOP.

Fig. 4 illustrates the distribution of the LHS samples for the IBAP price, which was sampled from a lognormal distribution fitted using a percentile-matching approach, and is used in Monte Carlo simulations. The plot demonstrates how the 100 samples are effectively spread across the specified uncertainty space, ensuring comprehensive coverage for this critical parameter. This systematic sampling approach is crucial for accurately propagating the uncertainty of the IBAP price through the techno-economic model, ensuring a balance between accuracy and computational feasibility.

3.3. Optimization problem formulation

We define the optimization problem as minimizing the LCOP. The LCOP represents the average cost per unit of the product that would need to be realized over the project's lifetime for the net present value

(NPV) to be zero, effectively serving as a break-even price. This metric discounts future costs and revenues to present value, providing a comprehensive cost assessment over the project's lifetime, calculated as follows:

$$LCOP = \frac{TCI \times CRF + OPEX_{\text{annual}}}{m_{\text{ibuprofen,annual}}} \quad (8)$$

Where TCI is the total capital investment, $OPEX_{\text{annual}}$ is the total annual operating cost, $m_{\text{ibuprofen,annual}}$ is the mass of ibuprofen produced annually, and CRF is the capital recovery factor calculated as follows:

$$CRF = \frac{r(1+r)^n}{(1+r)^n - 1} \quad (9)$$

Where r is the discount rate, and n is the project lifetime. The economic model integrates equipment sizing and costing scaled by the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI), directly within the AVEVA™ simulation environment. TCI is estimated using the Lang factor method to account for installation, piping, and indirect costs and includes equipment purchase costs and initial palladium inventory. OPEX incorporates raw material, solvent, and utility prices, as well as catalyst service fees for metal recovery and resynthesis to account for catalyst deactivation and recycling losses, and labor and maintenance costs.

The global market demand for ibuprofen is estimated to be approximately 26 thousand tonnes in 2025, and we perform the optimization over key design and operating variables to achieve a production target of ~20% of projected global demand for 2025, assuming 7920 operating hours per year (ChemAnalyst, 2025a; 2025b). The decision variables include reactor volumes, operating temperatures, and the solvent's feed ratios. These are all critical decision variables that influence residence time, reaction conversion, overall production yield, and economic performance. Therefore, optimizing these variables is essential for ensuring both process performance and economic feasibility robustly, guiding engineers towards optimal design and operating choices. We define the bounds for variables based on engineering judgement and reported experimental ranges, ensuring chemical reaction feasibility within validated operational windows that are presented in Table S7 in the Supplementary Material. We treat reactor volumes as discrete variables to reflect industrial equipment sizing constraints, and temperatures and solvents feed ratios as continuous variables.

Optimization is subject to inequality constraints. The first constraint enforces a minimum overall process yield, calculated based on the mass of pure ibuprofen obtained after downstream processing, to ensure high efficiency across both reaction and separation stages. We also impose additional constraints on reactor residence times based on the kinetics and selectivity behavior of each reaction to ensure process feasibility and support efficient optimization. For hydrogenation, a minimum residence time of 15 min is applied to ensure sufficient conversion and mixing performance, while longer times are naturally avoided due to the increased formation of side products that reduce selectivity. For carbonylation, a maximum residence time of 120 min is set to limit

Fig. 2. Continuous ibuprofen process flowsheet

Fig. 3. SRC values for top 15 influential parameters

Fig. 4. Latin hypercube sampling with 100 real values

reactor size and cost, while still allowing the reaction to reach high conversion, which favors the desired product. Accordingly, we formulate the resulting optimization problem as follows, where x represents the key decision variables:

$$\text{minimize}_x E [LCOP]$$

$$Ibuprofen \text{ yield} \geq 0.6$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tau_{hydrogenation} \geq 15 \text{ minutes}$$

$$\tau_{carbonylation} \leq 120 \text{ minutes}$$

under

$$\text{minimize}_x E [LCOP]$$

$$Ibuprofen \text{ yield} \geq 0.6$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tau_{hydrogenation} \geq 15 \text{ minutes}$$

$$\tau_{carbonylation} \leq 120 \text{ minutes}$$

(10)

under

$$IBAP_{price} \} \text{Lognormal}(\mu, \sigma^2)$$

In addition to the optimization constraints, we enforce equality constraints such as solvent recycling ratios and separation performance targets to ensure process feasibility and maintain consistent product quality and operational reliability through well-defined process conditions.

3.4. Simulation-based optimization under uncertainty

The optimization framework begins by constructing a surrogate model using 25 initial design points generated via LHS, ensuring broad and representative coverage of the input space. An adaptive sampling strategy follows, where new design points are selected iteratively based on the mcFEI infill criterion. For each sampling point, we perform 100 Monte Carlo simulations to capture uncertainty, and the mean values of these simulations are used to update the surrogate model. This approach balances exploration and exploitation, enabling efficient navigation of complex, uncertain design spaces while maintaining computational feasibility. The optimization concludes after 75 adaptive sampling iterations, selecting the best-performing design.

3.5. Techno-economic evaluation

The framework concludes with a techno-economic evaluation based on the optimized design. We assess economic performance during optimization using the economic indicator LCOP, evaluating constraints and objectives over multiple uncertainty scenarios. We compare the resulting LCOP value against the current market prices of ibuprofen to assess the economic feasibility of the optimized design. This integrated approach ensures that the final design is both cost-efficient and reliable under uncertain conditions, supporting the confident adoption of the new technology.

4. Results and discussion

To benchmark the benefits of incorporating uncertainty, we also conduct deterministic optimization. In the deterministic approach, we evaluate three key scenarios to represent the IBAP price uncertainty: the base-case scenario using the mean value of the uncertainty distribution, the best-case scenario, and the worst-case scenario. These serve as representative -10% and $+30\%$ shifts from the base-case price, allowing benchmarking of the deterministic response against the broader uncertainty range explored in the stochastic framework. Deterministic optimization employs Feasibility-Enhanced Expected Improvement (FEI) as the infill criterion instead of the mcFEI infill criterion, enabling effective surrogate-based search in constrained design spaces. We evaluate each design point with a single simulation run, whereas in the stochastic case, we perform multiple Monte Carlo simulations to account for uncertainty. In the deterministic case, we train Gaussian Process models using simulation outputs, without incorporating noise predictions or Monte Carlo-derived variability. In contrast, the stochastic framework uses Stochastic Kriging, training separate Gaussian Process models to capture both the mean response and the

associated variance from Monte Carlo simulations, enabling uncertainty-aware optimization and, therefore, a more robust design.

Figs. 5a and 5b illustrate the optimization progress over adaptive sampling iterations for the deterministic base-case and stochastic case, respectively. In the deterministic case, objective values improve more rapidly, as the model aggressively exploits the design space based on single-point evaluations. In contrast, the stochastic optimization progress shows a more conservative improvement curve due to the integrated uncertainty analysis. The objective values in the stochastic case demonstrate a path that prioritizes robustness from the outset, as the surrogate model is initialized and updated using Monte Carlo simulations that incorporate variability. The stochastic approach ensures that the selected design performs well across a range of possible parameter realizations, even if its convergence appears slower on the progress plot compared to the deterministic case. This hedging behavior prioritizes feasibility and robustness over aggressive cost reduction.

Notably, by the end of the adaptive iterations shown in Fig. 5, the deterministic optimization yields a lower LCOP of \$5782/tonne when evaluated at the base price compared to the stochastic optimization's LCOP of \$5983/tonne. While the deterministic approach, by ignoring variability, can identify a numerically lower point solution, this solution may be less robust or even fragile when faced with real-world fluctuations in IBAP prices, as seen with the results of the best-case and worst-case scenarios. The stochastic optimization, by explicitly incorporating uncertainty, leads to a more reliable and robust solution that performs well across a range of possible conditions. This comparison highlights the importance of integrating uncertainty quantification into technology shifts and strategic process development, as a seemingly lower LCOP from deterministic optimization might not be sustainable under real-world variability, whereas the stochastic solution provides a more resilient design.

Table 1 presents the optimal decision variable values: hydrogenation and carbonylation reactor volumes, operating temperatures, and solvent feed ratios (representing decane-to-IBAP ratio and MEK-to-IBAP ratios, respectively) obtained from both deterministic and stochastic optimization. The deterministic method yields different optimum values for the decision variables depending on the specific scenario being optimized. As the IBAP price increases from the best to the worst-case scenario, the deterministic optimum attempts to mitigate the economic impact of high feedstock costs on the LCOP by decreasing the operating temperatures, reducing the decane-to-IBAP ratio, and ultimately decreasing the carbonylation reactor volume while maintaining the required production throughput.

This counterintuitive behavior arises directly from the hydrogenation reaction kinetics. Although higher temperatures increase the intrinsic rate constants for all reactions, they however promote parallel

Fig. 5. (a) Deterministic optimization progress (b) Stochastic optimization progress

Table 1
Optimal decision variables and corresponding LCOP for deterministic and stochastic scenarios.

	Decision Variable	Optimal Value	Best Feasible LCOP
Deterministic Best-Case (\$2700/tonne)	Volume of the Reactors	2 m ³ & 15 m ³	\$5562/tonne
	Temperature of the Reactors	345.9 K & 397.9 K	
	Solvent Feed Ratios	0.169 & 0.1	
Deterministic Base-Case (\$3000/tonne)	Volume of the Reactors	2 m ³ & 15 m ³	\$5782/tonne
	Temperature of the Reactors	327.9 K & 386.2 K	
	Solvent Feed Ratios	0.1 & 0.1	
Deterministic Worst-Case (\$3900/tonne)	Volume of the Reactors	2 m ³ & 10 m ³	\$6754/tonne
	Temperature of the Reactors	323.1 K & 381.8 K	
	Solvent Feed Ratios	0.1 & 0.1	
Stochastic	Volume of the Reactors	2 m ³ & 10 m ³	\$5983/tonne
	Temperature of the Reactors	333.5 K & 391.5 K	
	Solvent Feed Ratios	0.184 & 0.128	

side-product (oligomer) formation (Eq. 3). This results in increased consumption of the expensive IBAP feedstock for undesired reactions, thereby lowering both IBPE yield and the overall ibuprofen yield. Fig. 6 presents a one-at-a-time sensitivity analysis of the hydrogenation reactor temperature on parallel side-product selectivity, IBPE yield (after hydrogenation), and overall ibuprofen yield (after purification) across the operational temperature bounds specified in Table S7. All other design variables are fixed at their nominal values (hydrogenation reactor volume=2 m³, carbonylation reactor volume=10 m³ operated at 380 K, solvent feed ratios=0.1). The figure shows that the parallel side-product selectivity increases with temperature, causing a monotonic decline in both yields. The shaded region highlights the optimal temperature window identified across the three deterministic optimization cases, where byproduct formation remains effectively controlled. Because the process must meet a fixed annual production target, any drop in yield requires a compensatory increase in IBAP feed rate, which reduces residence time. As a result, when the IBAP price rises, the optimizer systematically favors milder conditions to preserve selectivity

and minimize feedstock waste, thereby balancing capital and operating expenses to minimize the LCOP.

While operating variables can be adjusted to address the price uncertainty, it requires a continuous cycle of monitoring feedstock prices, running new deterministic optimizations, validating setpoints, and physically adjusting the process. This introduces operational overhead and forces the plant into frequent transient periods. Furthermore, design specifications such as reactor volumes are fixed capital decisions at the construction stage and cannot be easily modified, in contrast to operational tuning of temperatures and flow rates, which can be adjusted but incur overhead and efficiency trade-offs during transients.

On the other hand, stochastic optimization identifies a single robust design that satisfies yield and residence time constraints, while keeping the LCOP competitive. Additionally, stochastic optimization favors slightly different reactor temperatures and solvent feed ratios compared to the deterministic ones. This difference reflects a more conservative design that balances cost-efficiency with robustness under uncertain economic conditions. This comparison illustrates how accounting for uncertainty can influence equipment design and operating conditions, leading to a design that, while potentially having a slightly higher LCOP in a single-point comparison, is more resilient to real-world variability and does not require frequent adjustments. This highlights the distinction between short-term operational tuning and long-term strategic process design.

Notably, the stochastic optimization yields an LCOP of \$5983/tonne, which is well below the current market price of ibuprofen, standing at approximately \$10700/tonne (ChemAnalyst, 2025a; 2025b). This market price is largely reflective of the costs associated with traditional batch production processes that currently dominate the pharmaceutical industry, indicating the economic competitiveness of the proposed continuous process design. Additionally, a previous TEA of a continuous ibuprofen manufacturing process by Mustafa et al. (2022) for a similar industrial scale of 5000 tonnes per year reported a unit production cost of \$11,330/tonne. While differences in chemical pathways contribute to this variance, our results demonstrate that our proposed design and integrated framework, by explicitly accounting for uncertainties, can lead to more economically favorable and robust process designs. Moreover, the stochastic solution satisfies all performance and economic constraints under uncertainty, supporting its reliability for guiding investment decisions for continuous manufacturing technologies.

Fig. 6. Effect of hydrogenation reactor temperature on hydrogenation parallel side-product selectivity, IBPE yield and overall ibuprofen yield

5. Conclusions and future work

The study presents a framework to conduct a robust and comprehensive TEA of new pharmaceutical processes and technologies, including rigorous process modeling and simulations, global sensitivity analysis, uncertainty analysis, and optimization of key variables under uncertainties. We apply and demonstrate the framework on the ibuprofen continuous manufacturing process.

Rather than optimizing only for maximum yield, the framework prioritizes economic feasibility by minimizing the LCOP while enforcing a minimum process yield constraint. This approach reflects the industry's emphasis on cost efficiency for successful new technology adoption, ensuring that the final design is both economically viable and technically robust. Global sensitivity analysis identifies IBAP price as the most influential parameter, which accounts for the majority of the variance in the LCOP, guiding where to prioritize uncertainty quantification. The inclusion of this uncertainty provides a more comprehensive understanding of process economics.

The framework, coupled with Monte Carlo simulations for uncertainties, proved to be a valuable tool for addressing uncertainties and enhancing the robustness and reliability of the optimization of pharmaceutical processes. Pharmaceutical processes are sensitive to variations in conditions and parameters; therefore, identifying optimal solutions that perform well across a range of likely outcomes enhances the adaptability to real-world variations and supports informed decisions regarding technology shifts.

This framework can support informed decision-making and accurate cost estimation for new process technologies in development, where uncertainties are significant and robust solutions are crucial. By explicitly incorporating variability, the proposed framework reduces the risk of overestimating profitability and underestimating costs, thereby providing greater confidence in strategic design and investment decisions. The findings can contribute to the ongoing efforts in pharmaceutical manufacturing to achieve greener, more sustainable, and cost-effective processes by facilitating their transition.

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Data Availability Statement

The software tool MOSKopt_Python that supports the findings of this study is openly available in GitHub at https://github.com/gsi-lab/MOSKopt_Python. AVEVA™ Process Simulation file with custom libraries and the optimization scripts to run the developed tool for the ibuprofen case study have been included as example templates in the repository.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.chemd.2026.06.051](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemd.2026.06.051).

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